

1. Preparation
welcoming altitude, weather, wind aim access to water parking, regulations

2. Team
mindset, health condition dive experience certifications, insurance buoyancy, equalization SAC rate, finning

3. Equipment
BCD mount, cylinders suit, hood, weights computer, compass reels, DSMBs, lights, cutters batteries, camera heat, sun, wind protection

4. Emergency
call: VHF 16, phone Euro 112 DAN Euro: +39 06 42 11 56 85 oxygen kit first aid kit, defibrilator near hospital near hyperbaric centre

5. Dive site
dangers temperature current visibilty entry and exit morphology, depths

6. Dive plan
profile MOD / END rule of gases time / max TTS GF
route travel, bottom, deco heading, reference points animals, plants ascent: DSMBs, safety stops
alternatives no deco +3 min +3 m
groups check config gases and marking
start S-drill, Team equip matchup Air, Route, Table

7. Coordination
reminders no dive or ending dive is ok exhale, stay close signal discomforts
hand signs ok / problem / up / down / end pressure, no gas breathlessness freezing, cold DSMB, TTS, deco stop
torch / touch / rope / audio
procedures lost buddy lost geo deco broken (GF99) SIPE lost / failed material marine life injury

Gas switch
Signal W atch depth I dentify T urn on C onfirm depth on cylinder C hange regulator C hange computer H ang time begin

Notes
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